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CONCEPT OF MOONLIGHTING AND ITS CAUSES AND IMPACT ON ORGANIZATION'S GROWTH

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Abstract:

Human resource is considered as the important asset for any organization. The management of the firm faces a difficulty in attracting and keeping human resources as the economy expands and becomes more competitive on a worldwide scale. Multiple-job holding is increased particularly in recent time. Through this article the authors examine drivers of multiple-job holding.

An employee holding two jobs, one is regular and other is part timer, doing secretly that is called moon lighting. Although the term "moonlighting" has many different connotations, it primarily refers to working a job covertly, usually at night. It is also known as act of doing a second job without telling your current employer. Through this research author tried to explain meaning of moonlighting, its causes and impact on organization's growth. Also, through this research researcher identified different measures to avoid issues related to moonlighting.

Key word: Moonlighting, Code of Ethics, Additional income, startup, skills

Introduction:

The term "moonlighting" refers to the practice of working for one organization while also taking on additional duties and employment, usually without the employer's knowledge. The term "side job" refers to a job that is often done after hours or on the weekends. When Americans started seeking for second occupations in addition to their usual 9-to-5 work to support their income, the expression gained notoriety.

Moonlighting is categorized into four categories as blue moon, quarter moon, half moon, and full moon.

"Doing two remote jobs at once was already happening; it was the biggest open secret out there in tech," a US techie was quoted by The Guardian as saying.

After major IT companies like Infosys, TCS, and Wipro said they would delay, postpone or reduce the variable payout to employees for the first quarter of the fiscal year 2023 due to weaker margins, moonlighting garnered attention.

In India, it's legal to hold multiple jobs without breaching the law. However, a person with a comparable set of employment could raise worries about a breach of confidence because many employers often forbid employees from holding down more than one job in their employment agreements.

Objectives:

1. To understand the concept of moonlight practices
2. To identify the causes of moonlighting
3. To understand the impact of moonlighting on Organizational Growth
3. To identify measures to counter the problems of moonlighting

Research Methodology:

Secondary data has been used, articles, journals, research papers, review papers, articles and internet sources. This paper studied several aspects related to moonlighting in an organization.

Literature Review

Steven d. Culler, gloria i. Bazzoli (1985), the resident doctors' choices about their side jobs. This study analyses factors that influence doctors' decisions to moonlight during their training. According to the study, family and personal background play a significant role, which includes

marital status, sex, age, gender and the time spent with children plays a major role which determines working hours. the study concluded that the above factors are all important to decision making whether to take a second job or not.

Karen Smith Conway, Jean Kimmel (1992), Moonlighting Behavior: Theory and Evidence. The study suggest that the employees choose moonlighting because of diverse jobs these are considered to be primary motivations for moonlighting the behavior in employees act as akey role in moonlighting.

Deborah Sussman (1998), Moonlighting: A growing way of life the study states that according to the increasing needs of people the reasons may be diverserendering to each and every individual. Over the past two years women moonlighting are more. The paper concluded that different age groups, employment opportunities, drawn to moonlighting for a number of monetary and non-monetary benefits in order to increase their salary and also gain experience in work.

Gordon Cohn Hershey H. Friedman (2002), In his study authorexplained the relationship between employee and employer and how employers control their employees in order to motivate them, paying wages according to the work done by them, providing benefits the study found out that the employers must treat their employees fairly in order to achieve the organizational goal and also to build strong relationship between employer and employee.

Semion and Adebisi (2019) studied that professional and managerial level employees of public sectors are more engaged in moonlighting. His findings suggest that moonlighting promoting disloyal and discontent workforce, encouraged bureaucracy, promote leisure attitude towards job, inefficient leadership, and ineffective organisational policies. He suggested that necessary rules and controls by government should be taken to prohibit moonlighting in public sectors.

Sabron& Hassim (2018) concluded that public sector employees had high rates of moonlighting engagement. They examined the employee's perception on moonlighting practices in for Malaysian public sector hospitals. The study was conducted to determine the environment, personal and behavioural factors that are related to the employees practicing moonlighting. The findings obtained that personal factor and environment factor had a positive and significant relationship towards employee's engagement in moonlighting and concluded that it is complex to implement moonlighting in an organization for employers and it is also time consuming. The results also state that environment factor and personal factor influences employee more to be

engaged in moonlighting and recommended that government should offer part time basis admin job also so employees can learn new things.

Ara and Akbar (2016) explained the effect of moonlighting practices on job satisfaction of public universities teachers in Pakistan. They identified four factors that are skill diversity, blocked promotion, job autonomy, and additional income responsible for moonlighting among university teachers. They explicated that there is a substantial impact of moonlighting on job satisfaction.

KaukabAra and Aisha Akbar (2016),in this Study the author has examined that moonlighting have an impact on satisfaction of job where it comes from pay scale; appraisal/promotions, skills, all are tested in this study. The study concludes that because of lack of pay scale, skills, promotions, appraisal which lead to reduced level of satisfaction in job.

Shweta (2014) studied the different aspects of moonlighting of employees. She analyzed various issues related to moonlighting and explained the need to understand why employees moonlight. She provided recommendations for employers and employees for preventing moonlighting.

Ashwini et al studied the drivers for moonlighting in IT sector. The person engaged in moonlighting either for monetary or non- monetary motives. They found that people moonlight to deal with their financial problem or increased financial obligations in their family to satisfy the non-monetary priorities. The employees do the secondary job according to their free time not only for motives. Total numbers of hours spend in secondary jobs and monetary, non-monetary motives might be the factor for deciding moonlighting types and its extent. They identified that many factors can lead to employees towards multiple job holding and number of family members is the major factor of it. The study also said that intention to moonlight varied from married to unmarried employees. Work experience is an important factor that led to the intention to moonlight. Moonlighting motives are also dependent on demographic factors.

Puja Khatri and Khushboo (2014) have looked at SME employees in Delhi-NCR's organizational commitment and side-hustling habits. This study looks at how employees feel about the organization's commitment policies and sidejobs.Complementary results to differentiate between female and male and also to manage attrition rate of employees. The study discovered that while employees in SME divisions are aware of emerging trends, SME's still lag behind in funding and technological advancement, which makes employees less dedicated to their jobs and more likely to moonlight (take on a second job).

Laetitia C. Rispel, Duane Blaauw, Tobias Chirwa and katinka de wet (2013), factors influencing agency nursing and moonlighting among South African nurses; the study is focused on the health-related factors. Health care provider's the best performance is dangerous for successful achievement of reforms of health sector the study found out that overtime of nurses and factors which influences them to moonlighting these all are common among African nurses these have received inadequate strategy notice.

Alessandro Fedele and Paolo Naticchioni in 2013: Moonlighting Politicians: Motivation Matters was conducted. The study looks at the greatest options for picking politicians and their dedication to that particular job. Politicians can also moonlight, participate in market-related activities, and serve as members of parliament. and comes to the conclusion that politicians take opportunity cost seriously.

Banerjee (2012): Moonlighting was categorized into four categories as blue moon, quarter moon, half moon, and full moon.

Heather Dickey, Verity Watson and Alexandros Zangelidis (2011), Is it all about money? An examination of the motives behind moonlighting. The author examines from the study that family background plays a major role for moonlighting. The paper comes to the conclusion that people who choose moonlighting or numerous jobs do so as a result of financial difficulties in their families and growing financial responsibilities in their houses.

Betts (2011) studied on the gender differences among teachers who do moonlighting. He found that male and female teachers have different patterns of moonlighting behavior. According to pay, type and prevalence of moonlighting activity differences were noticed.

Gayatri observed that moonlighting helps to increase the standard of living of employees and employees try to test their skills in different job. Job satisfaction and monetary benefits can avoid moonlighting. She found the impact of moonlighting on employer as well as employee. Moonlighting can lead to misbalance of physical and psychological needs of an employee. Employees may also moonlight to gain more experience in different jobs or to start a new business. Employer can provide monetary as well as non-monetary benefits to motivate the employees and avoid moonlighting. Job rotation and job security by employer can also help employee to avoid moonlighting.

Georgios et al (2011) studied the dynamics of human capital, dual job holding, and occupational choice between primary and secondary jobs were investigated. The determinants and factors

affecting secondary job were also studied. He also studied the effects of multiple jobs holding on primary jobs. Their research indicated that dual job holding may also lead to self-employment and new primary jobs.

Susan L. Averett (2010), Averett (2010) The study focuses on the factors that influence whether men and women choose to work more than one job and moonlight. the study founded that both men and women are less likely to say income the reasons for motivation to moonlighting varies according to gender to gender.

Larry Buhl Moonlighting: Pros and Cons of a Second Job According to the study, there are drawbacks to moonlighting that you should try to overcome, including employer annoyance, time commitment, conflict, and a lack of money, security, freedom, and skills. choose an unrelated field and look for some part-time work.

Ritu Tiwari (2014), Moonlighting and Putting in Place Measures to stop it: The author attempts to find the reasons why people moonlight and what measures organization can take to control it.

Shweta Sangwan (2014), Managing Employee Moonlighting: Issues and Implications, according to the study, moonlighting has both drawbacks and advantages when ethical questions are also raised. it is a challenging task for both employees and employer the study says that without conflict in the organization between employee and employer should maintain good relationship.

Gabriel Montes-Rojas Sarmistha Pal (2015), Public Pain and Private Gain: An Analysis of Moonlighting by Public Health Professionals, the study found that public health professionals frequently hold different roles to gain position and monetary benefits.

Causes:

- Extra source of income
Moonlighting allows employee to earn more, which decreases the pressure on the employer to increase the wages. Hence it decreases the financial burden on the organization.
- Broad exposure and opportunity to work in different roles and projects
- Opportunity to grow skill set
- Widened professional network
- Having enough money to weather financial turbulence like layoffs

- To improve the living standard
- To combat with boredom
- To follow passion
- Moonlighting for Startups

Impact of Moonlighting on the Organization:

Moonlighting poses various challenges for the management. It has both positive and negative impacts on an organization. Several issues which came in light due to moonlighting are discussed below:

1. **Low Productivity** When employees are engaged in two or more jobs, their performance hampers because of the lack of focus on the current job. So their productivity decreases which leads to incompleteness of tasks.

2. **Loss of Business Privacy and Competition Threat** When employees do other job with the current job or start his own venture similar to the current job there is a competition threat for the present employer. Conflict of interest may arise between them. The present employer could also be anxious about his business privacy and confidentiality.

3. **Employees Well Being** Employees engaged in more jobs feel exhausted in terms of physical and mental health. They face anxiety and fatigue related health issues. So these employees are unable to perform best in their jobs. Due to overburdened work they may face various health issues.

4. **Ethical Issues** An ethical dilemma arises when an employee does moonlight in the same industry. If employee shares information from both the employers then the problem arises. It results in sharing of confidential information of the business. Also, if any employee uses both physical and intellectual resources of the company for the other company then the ethical problem arises. Hence it may be considered as theft.

How to tackle:

There is a divided opinion about moonlighting, as employers and employees have different approaches. Before choosing to moonlight, employees should be open and honest about their concerns. Employers can choose from a variety of methods, including taking regular feedback, offering training sessions, and introducing policies to control moonlighting. Finding a fair solution will assist in retaining competent staff and fostering long-lasting connections.

The ethical code is designed to help employees recognize and deal with ethical issues in their work. policy is to behave with integrity while dealing with our customers, adhere to all applicable rules and regulations, and be dedicated to conducting business ethically with customers, suppliers, partners, competitors, employees and other stakeholders. The guide to help whenever you have questions about ethics or if you are faced with an ethical dilemma.

Primarily, it is significant that the employer plans who will be covered by the moonlighting policy. Typically, employers choose to bound the scope of their moonlighting policy to all full-time employees. However, an employer can decide which employees will be covered based on their business needs. For example, an employer may extend a moonlighting policy to part-time employees who are required to work at least 25 hours a week and are on a salary.

It must also be noted that it is good practice for employers to also state that their policy applies to legal activities. Further, it is not uncommon to state that legal action may be taken against employees that use their employer's resources to conduct illegal activities.

A moonlighting policy is beneficial because it can increase employee productivity. There are numerous ways that an employee's external work can adversely affect the business. For example: With a moonlighting policy, as there is a shift in prioritization, employees will better focus on employer's tasks which could increase the overall productivity of a business. To control moonlighting use of strategic and considerate steps and employing operative methods like the following can help.

Take regular feedback

Ask for input frequently to find out if workers feel underpaid or uneasy about potential layoffs. Their response will reveal any lingering issues in their minds and reveal how they view their job.

Carry out thorough background checks

Companies can prevent moonlighting by conducting background checks on prospective employees on a regular basis. Checking EPFO will reveal any further contributions and provide details. It aids in ascertaining any concurrent work status.

Additionally, businesses can collaborate with analytics and security firms to conduct audits and monitor any suspicious activity.

Provide necessary training to develop skills

Employers must determine whether their staff members are learning or require extra training in order to acquire the skills they need to succeed.

Without adequate learning and development support, workers are urged to choose side employment that provide better career prospects and financial security. As a result, it's essential to do a skill gap analysis and meet the training requirements.

Interferes with the principal employment

Most moonlighting policies are primarily intended to outline your expectations that workers will treat their work for your company as their primary job and won't allow other occupations to interfere with it.

Consider include this clause in your policy. You are not required to limit a worker's access to alternative employment options. Simply stating that you expect the employee to put your job first is sufficient.

Conflict of interest. To secure your business, policies are necessary in part. A conflict-of-interest policy can assist you in preventing employees from beginning to work for your rivals while they are still employed by you.

Approval of employment. In formulating your moonlighting policy, you may want to include a clause that states that an employee must get approval for any outside employment. If you do include this clause, be sure that it isn't too restrictive and that you apply it consistently to all employees — don't allow one person to work another job and prohibit another employee from doing so if circumstances are similar.

Basic moonlighting policies generally contain the statements addressing:

- Interference with the primary job
- Conflicts of interest
- Your approval of the additional employment

Avoid Conflict of interest:

Financial or non-financial dealing with related party

Hiring of relatives in same chain of command.

Employees are permitted to deliver lectures at/write articles for educational institutions or professional forums provided it does not create a conflict of interest with any Company

If you employee is invited for delivering lecture,the content [of lecture or article] should not be objectionable or confidential.

The employee should keep the Line Manager and the HR representative pre-informed,who should notethe same in the employee's personnel record.

Outside employment

vocation, employment. consultancy. training assignment. business transaction

Exceptions:

Directorships or advisory board positions on charitable organisations (certified by Income Tax Authority) or professional industry forums. Employees must keep the HR representative pre-informed. Any remuneration is not permitted. Any exceptions will require written pre-approval from the Executive Chairman and Group HR Head. Employees will not be permitted to accept any remuneration in monetary or in non-monetary form. In case any remuneration is received in non-monetary form it should be in line with the Company's Policy on Gifts and Entertainment.

Outside investments

An employee or any relative [parents/ spouse / dependent children] should not make or hold an investment directly or indirectly in any unlisted private entity, startup business entity that competes with, does business with, or is seeking to do business with the Company

Involvement in political activities

The Company does not support any specific political party and does not have any political affiliation. Therefore, no contributions should be made, on behalf of the Company, either directly

or indirectly, to any political party or for any political purpose without prior approval of the Board of Directors.

We cannot use our job title or Company affiliation in connection with political activities.

We should ensure that we do not give an impression of representing or being the spokesperson of the Company while getting associated with any political party or political activities in our personal capacity.

Gifts and entertainment

We do not permit acceptance or offering of gifts (refer Appendix 1, Glossary 6 for definition) from past, current, or prospective customers, suppliers, distributors, dealers, consultants or fellow employees of the company (except on the occasion of a marriage – from fellow employees; or upon retirement). We may accept an invitation to a meal, entertainment or a sports event which is within the scope of social formality and not excessively extravagant, expensive or frequent.

Antitrust and competition law

We seek to compete fairly, ethically, and within the framework of all applicable competition laws. Anticompetitive practices can damage the business and reputation of the Company. • The competition laws protect competition by prohibiting anti-competitive behaviour. This behaviour may include: – Entering into anti-competitive agreements with competitors, including price-fixing, bid-rigging, market allocation and agreements to restrict supply. – Exchanging sensitive information (refer glossary 7 for definition) with competitors

Protection and responsible use of corporate assets and information technology

Everyone at the Company is personally responsible for safeguarding, securing, and protecting the Company's assets and information technology from theft, destruction, misappropriation, wastage and abuse. Our assets include property, time, proprietary information, corporate opportunities, Company funds, and Company equipment.

Protect confidential information of the Company, its employees, and its business associates

During the course of work, we may have access to confidential information about the Company. 'Confidential Information' is generally non-public and/or personally identifiable information (refer glossary 11 for definition) that employees may be aware of as a result of their position with the Company and that might be of use to competitors or harmful to the Company if disclosed. Common examples include:

Company Intellectual Property The intellectual property (IP) of the Company must be protected as a vital business asset. Our IP portfolio includes copyrights, patents, trademarks, service marks, trade secrets, design rights, logos, brands and know-how. We must use our IP focusing on protecting these assets. It is important to ensure that to the extent permitted by law, the rights to all IP created using the Company's time and expense that which are within the scope of our duties are assigned to and are the property of the Company

The use of assets for individual profit or any unlawful, unauthorized personal or unethical purpose is prohibited. Our information technology, intellectual property (e.g., copyrights, patents, and trademarks), facilities, equipment, machines, software, and cash may be used for business purposes only, including responsible and accurate expense reimbursement, and in accordance with applicable policies. Other assets (e.g., computers, printers, and copiers) may be used for minor and incidental personal purposes provided such use is kept to a minimum, and does not create any significant incremental costs, interfere with work duties, or violate any laws or Infosys policies. The use of any Infosys resources for personal political activities is prohibited. Computer hardware, software, data, and facilities are valuable resources that need protection from potential destruction, theft, or misuse. These resources may also include confidential client or Infosys information that requires safeguarding. It is your responsibility to prevent unauthorized access through the use of ID badges, passwords, or other security codes, and physical security measures (such as using computer cable locks, not leaving computers unattended in cars, and other normal precautions). Copyrighted materials (e.g., books, music, software, and magazines) should not be reproduced, distributed, or altered without permission of the copyright owner or an authorized agent. Software used in connection with the business of Infosys should be properly licensed and used only in accordance with that license. Using unlicensed software could constitute copyright infringement and may be grounds for disciplinary action. For more information, please read the Company's policies on use of Company assets

Conclusion:

Human resource management plays a strategic role in managing people and workplace environment. The person engaged in moonlighting either for monetary or non-monetary motives. Appropriate policies must be framed to overcome the effects of moonlighting and maintaining transparent and harmonious relationship between employer and employees in an organization. This study has contributed to a small extent to create awareness about moonlighting, its causes, impact and measures to avoid negative impact of moonlighting.

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